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ALGORITHMIC WEATHER MODEL OPTIMISATION
BASED ON ENSEMBLE FORECASTING

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Helsinki, June 2023

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Abstract

Algorithmic model optimisation is a promising approach to yield the best possible forecast performance of multi-scale multi-phase atmospheric models once the model structure has been fixed. Algorithmic methods are intended to decrease the need for laborious and time consuming manual optimisation. This thesis explores different aspects related to ensemble forecasting-based optimisation of numerical weather prediction models using OpenIFS weather model as an example. This thesis firstly presents tools and initial states data to perform academic ensemble forecasting experiments. Secondly, making optimisation experiments efficiently is discussed and demonstrated. Thirdly, a potential observation-based ensemble verification method to be used in future tuning experiments is presented and discussed.

Development and testing of tools required in ensemble forecasting-based algorithmic optimisation is presented first. The tuning experimentation in this thesis requires a comprehensive set of initial states and a workflow management system that enables automatic ensemble forecasting, cost function evaluation and parameter sampling. A year of initial states for OpenIFS weather model is created. The dataset contains initial states twice daily for three model resolutions. An open-source workflow manager is presented and demonstrated with various ensemble forecasting experiments.

The forecasting tool and initial states are used to study different aspects of ensemble forecasting-based algorithmic optimisation. Firstly, parameter convergence is studied in a controlled test set-up in order to find out to what extent algorithmic optimisation can be trusted. Experimentation with the test set-up crystallises which conditions are sufficient to obtain reliable results and thus build confidence on the optimisation in fully-realistic cases. Output of the parameter convergence tests is condensed into a general guidance for algorithmic model optimisation. Secondly, the guidance is tested in fully-realistic optimisation experiments involving $O(20)$ most important uncertain parameters of OpenIFS. It is shown that optimisation with $O(20)$ ensemble members and $O(100)$ algorithm steps leads to substantially improved predictive skill. However, the results show that algorithmic optimisation has a number of shortcomings too.

Lastly, so-called filter likelihood score (FLS) is introduced. FLS is an observation-based ensemble forecast verification metric that could technically be used as cost function in model optimisation in the future. FLS is theoretically capable of addressing some shortcomings encountered during the tuning experiments of this thesis. Performance of FLS is demonstrated together with traditional verification metrics using different types of observations.

The results show that FLS is capable of indicating bias and inappropriate ensemble spread.

Keywords: ensemble forecasting, cost function, forecast skill, verification, EPPES

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List of publications

This thesis consists of an introductory review, followed by 4 research articles. **Papers I, II, and IV** are reprinted under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC-BY 4.0) license. **Paper III** is reprinted with permission from American Meteorological Society. In the introductory part, these papers are cited according to their roman numerals.

- I** Ollinaho, P., Carver, G.D., Lang, S.T.K., Tuppi, L., Ekblom, M., and Järvinen, H. (2021). Ensemble prediction using a new dataset of ECMWF initial states – OpenEnsemble 1.0, *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 14:2143–2160, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-14-2143-2021>
- II** Tuppi, L., Ollinaho, P., Ekblom, M., Shemyakin, V., and Järvinen, H. (2020). Necessary conditions for algorithmic tuning of weather prediction models using OpenIFS as an example, *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 13:5799–5812, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-13-5799-2020>
- III** Tuppi, L., Ekblom, M., Ollinaho, P., and Järvinen, H. (2023). Simultaneous Optimization of 20 Key Parameters of the Integrated Forecasting System of ECMWF Using OpenIFS. Part I: Effect on Deterministic Forecasts, *Monthly Weather Review*, 151:1325–1346, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1175/MWR-D-22-0209.1>.
- IV** Ekblom, M., Tuppi, L., Rätty, O., Ollinaho, P., Laine, M., and Järvinen, H. (2023). Filter Likelihood as an Observation-Based Verification Metric in Ensemble Forecasting, *Tellus A: Dynamic Meteorology and Oceanography*, 75(1):69-87, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.16993/tellusa.96>

List of abbreviations

AMSU-A	Advanced Microwave Sounding Unit A
CAM5	Community Atmosphere Model version 5
CAPE	Convective available potential energy
CRPS	Continuous ranked probability score
DE	Differential evolution
DSS	Dawid-Sebastiani score
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EDA	Ensemble of data assimilations
EPPES	Ensemble prediction and parameter estimation system
fCRPS	Fair continuous ranked probability score
FLS	Filter likelihood score
GHz	Gigahertz
hPa	Hectopascal
IFS	Integrated Forecasting System
McICA	Monte Carlo independent column approximation
NH	Northern hemisphere
NWP	Numerical weather prediction
NWP-SAF	NWP satellite application facility
OpenEPS	Open Ensemble Prediction System
OpenIFS	Open Integrated Forecasting System
RMSE	Root mean squared error
RMSE _{ens}	Ensemble mean RMSE
RTTOV	Radiative Transfer for TOVS
SH	Southern hemisphere
SPP	Stochastically perturbed parameters
SPPT	Stochastically perturbed parameterised tendencies
SV	Singular vector
TEMP	Conventional radio sounding
TR	Tropical region
UTC	Universal time coordinated
WRF3	Weather Research and Forecast Model version 3
ΔE_m	Moist total energy norm
ΔZ	RMSE of 850 hPa geopotential

1 Introduction

Solving future atmospheric states is based on numerical weather prediction (NWP). Evolution of the atmospheric state is governed by a coupled system of partial differential equations (see e.g. Eq. 2.1.19 - 2.1.23 in Kalnay, 2002). The system of equations describes the atmospheric motion, thermodynamics and evolution of water vapour. However, analytical solution for the system of equations is not known. Instead, the solution can be approximated with discrete numerical models. Discretisation means that only phenomena larger than the grid spacing can be solved explicitly but anything smaller than that must be included implicitly through mathematical process descriptions, referred to as parameterisations. These mathematical descriptions represent the subgrid-scale phenomena using resolved-scale quantities. The equations typically contain adjustable coefficients called closure or tuning parameters. Illustrations of parameterisations are shown below and in Section 2.

Available computational resources determine how small scales can be resolved explicitly in a discrete model. Typical grid spacing in NWP models is of the order of kilometres or tens of kilometres (Bauer et al., 2015; ECMWF, 2023). Therefore several everyday atmospheric phenomena like turbulent wind gusts, convective clouds, rain and radiation transfer cannot be represented explicitly using the grid because they can occur in between two grid points.

The need for parameterisation of sub-grid-scale phenomena can be illustrated using the primitive equations of the atmosphere. The first illustration considers the three-dimensional equation of motion

$$\frac{D\mathbf{U}}{Dt} = -2\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{U} - \frac{1}{\rho}\nabla p + \mathbf{g} + \mathbf{F} \quad (1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$ refers to rotation of the Earth, \mathbf{U} is three-dimensional wind, ρ is the density of air, ∇p is the pressure gradient, \mathbf{g} is the gravitational force and \mathbf{F} represents the frictional forces. In order to get a very simple example in cartesian coordinates, hydrostatic stability is assumed and other forces than horizontal pressure gradient and coriolis force are neglected. The next steps follow Holton and Hakim (2013). Reynolds averaging is used to divide the wind components u and v into grid mean and perturbation parts. In the case of horizontally homogeneous turbulence, the outcome can be written as

$$\frac{D\bar{u}}{Dt} = -\frac{1}{\rho_0}\frac{\partial\bar{p}}{\partial x} + f\bar{v} - \frac{\partial\overline{u'w'}}{\partial z} \quad (2)$$

and

$$\frac{D\bar{v}}{Dt} = -\frac{1}{\rho_0} \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial y} - f\bar{u} - \frac{\partial \overline{v'w'}}{\partial z} \quad (3)$$

where f denotes the coriolis parameter. These equations contain subgrid-scale covariances ($\overline{u'w'}$ and $\overline{v'w'}$) of the wind components, which represent turbulent vertical fluxes of momentum. $\overline{u'w'}$ and $\overline{v'w'}$ cannot be represented in a discrete grid due to the small scale of the phenomena. Instead, they must be parameterised using grid-scale quantities. A simple parameterisation of the covariances can be constructed using the first order turbulence closure scheme (also known as the K-theory, Monin and Obukhov, 1954). The covariances are parameterised using the mean wind

$$\frac{D\bar{u}}{Dt} = -\frac{1}{\rho_0} \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial x} + f\bar{v} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (K_m \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial z} \right)) \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{D\bar{v}}{Dt} = -\frac{1}{\rho_0} \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial y} - f\bar{u} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (K_m \left(\frac{\partial \bar{v}}{\partial z} \right)) \quad (5)$$

where K_m (m^2s^{-1}) is the eddy viscosity coefficient. However, K_m rather depends on the flow itself than the physical properties of the air, so representation of K_m in numerical models needs further elaboration. E.g. Monin and Obukhov (1954) and Stensrud (2007) present a detailed discussion how K_m can be described with grid-scale quantities. Even though parameterisation of boundary layer processes with K-theory appears simplistic, it is used at least in Integrated Forecasting System (IFS) of European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF, 2017).

Another illustration considers the first law of thermodynamics, which determines how different energy-related processes affect the heat content of the air

$$C_p \bar{\theta} \frac{d\bar{\theta}}{dt} = Q_{rad} - g \frac{\partial F_\theta}{\partial p} + L(C - E) \quad (6)$$

where C_p is the heat capacity of air in constant pressure, T is temperature, θ is potential temperature, Q_{rad} refers to radiative heating and cooling, g is the gravity constant, F_θ refers to sensible heat fluxes, L is the vaporisation energy, C condensation and E evaporation. None of the terms on the right-hand side can be solved explicitly but they need to be parametrised. Section 2 will discuss more about parametrised processes from the view-point of the NWP model used in this thesis.

Fully-fledged NWP models contain numerous similar physical processes that are parameterised. The parameterisations contained in atmospheric models are mostly related to boundary layer processes, turbulence, convection, clouds, precipitation generation

and radiation. Other model components beyond the atmospheric model contain more parameterised processes. For a comprehensive discussion about parameterisation of physical processes in NWP models see Stensrud (2007).

Parameterisations are always approximations of the real world physical processes, so some uncertainty related to the closure parameters always remains. Moreover, determination of optimal values for the parameters is often very challenging task for a number of reasons. Firstly, several closure parameters cannot be easily obtained from field measurements or laboratory experiments. Instead, other methods e.g. models with very fine grid must be used (Lohmann et al., 2007). However, these models are only representations of the truth as well. Secondly, the parameter interactions can be so strong that tuning the parameters one-by-one can lead to poor results (Qian et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2014). Thirdly, all fully-realistic models contain underlying compensating biases and complex non-linear interactions between different processes. Therefore, any change to the model structure or single parameterisation scheme can break the delicate balance and lead to a need to retune the entire model (Hourdin et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2013). Fourthly, behaviour of the parameterised physical processes can be resolution-dependent (Kanehama et al., 2022). Fifthly, optimal parameter values can be state and flow-dependent (Barton et al., 2019; Duan et al., 2017), and sixthly, all subgrid-scale processes are not represented well enough in the models (Schmidt et al., 2017).

Traditionally the tuning process has been carried out manually. However, the outcome of manual tuning is strongly dependent on the knowledge, personal experience and expertise of the practitioner. Therefore, the tuning process can be an opaque maze of subjective choices (see e.g. Mauritsen et al., 2012). Objective and transparent methods for tuning are highly desired, and one option is to use algorithmic tools. Therefore, this thesis concentrates on answering the question of how to determine optimal values for the closure parameters using algorithmic methods.

This question has already been explored before using various models and tuning algorithms. For example, papers considering technical aspects of algorithmic optimisation of a realistic model in a simplified framework include at least (Aksoy et al., 2006a,b; Annan et al., 2005a,b; Schirber et al., 2013). These papers use artificial fixed truth as a goal towards which the model is optimised. Papers related to fully-realistic optimisation include for instance, Duan et al. (2017) who optimised nine parameters in WRF3 model for summer season precipitation events in Beijing area using adaptive surrogate-

modelling-based optimisation. They were able to gain substantial improvements in precipitation and temperature. Yang et al. (2013) optimised nine parameters of the convection scheme of CAM5 model using simulated-annealing-based method. They were able to improve wind and precipitation climatology. More examples are found from other Earth system component models, e.g., Sumata et al. (2019) optimised 15 parameters of a sea ice model using a genetic algorithm, Fennel et al. (2001) used data assimilation for optimisation of 14 parameters in a marine ecosystem model, Gong et al. (2015) optimised 40 parameters of the common land model using adaptive surrogate modelling, and Wang et al. (2014) optimised 14 parameters of a hydrological model with surrogate modelling. Houtekamer et al. (2021) provides a different perspective as they optimised model parameters with the focus on improving ensemble forecasting capability instead of deterministic skill. Williamson et al. (2017) focused on ruling out bad parameter values instead of searching for optimal values.

1.1 Hypothesis and aims of the thesis

The main aim of this thesis is to advocate algorithm-based optimisation of NWP models but also to present examples of academic use cases for the datasets and tools developed. This thesis can be interpreted to provide guidance on successful ensemble forecasting and algorithmic optimisation exercises.

The specific aims or research questions related to the individual papers are detailed below:

1. How to run ensemble forecasts outside operational weather prediction centres? **Paper I** addresses this need by developing a database containing ensemble initial states for one year and by developing an easy-to-use ensemble forecasting workflow manager. The initial states are supposed to be used with OpenIFS weather model. However, the workflow manager can accommodate other models as well. Using the initial states and the workflow manager are demonstrated with experiments showing how different initial state perturbation configurations affect commonly used ensemble verification scores.

2. What circumstances favour successful algorithmic optimisation? In **Paper II**, a large number of optimisation experiments is carried out with different settings. The optimisation experiments use a fixed truth, unperturbed control model output, as

the reference. Hence, the set-up is more controlled than a fully-realistic optimisation experiment. Motivation of the research question arises from the computational cost of algorithmic optimisation. NWP models are computationally expensive to run so it is paramount in algorithmic model tuning that the method applied is able to converge to the correct statistics with limited computing resources. The aim of **Paper II** is to gauge the circumstances favouring successful model tuning when ensemble-based parameter estimation methods are used. The favourable circumstances are boiled down to a cook-book style recipe. **Paper II** explains how to start working on an optimisation problem, how to maximise efficiency and reproducibility, and what practical concerns exist. Lastly, performance of the recipe is demonstrated with more demanding optimisation experiments.

3. Is it possible to simultaneously estimate a large ($O(20)$) number of model parameters and achieve significant prediction skill improvement? The aim here is to demonstrate the practicality of optimising an NWP model while obtaining notable gain in the forecast skill. Simultaneous optimisation of large number of parameters is a challenging multi-dimensional problem. **Paper III** demonstrates how to tackle the problem with the cook-book recipe of **Paper II** in fully-realistic examples of algorithmic optimisation. Shortcomings related to algorithmic tuning are also discussed.

4. How to use an observation-based method (filter likelihood score, FLS) in verification of ensemble forecasts? What is the outlook for using a directly observation-based cost function in algorithmic optimisation in the future? These questions are answered by showing that FLS works in fully-realistic ensemble forecasting set-ups, and that it is in line with other more traditional ensemble verification metrics. **Paper IV** demonstrates using FLS for verification of ensemble forecasts using different initial state perturbation configurations and different ensemble sizes. An approximate multivariate FLS is also constructed from scores based on in-situ and satellite observations.

2 Key parameterisations in IFS/OpenIFS

Integrated Forecasting System (IFS) is the operational weather forecasting system at ECMWF, and it has been used since March 1994. IFS is a global semi-Lagrangian semi-implicit model with dynamics computed in spherical space and physical processes in grid point space. Subsection 2.1 presents the atmospheric component of IFS, and Subsection 2.2 gives an IFS-specific introduction to the most important parameterised physical processes that are thought to be uncertain.

2.1 OpenIFS

OpenIFS is the atmospheric forecasting model of ECMWF's IFS (ECMWF, 2017) dedicated for research and education purposes. OpenIFS has the same hydrostatic dynamical core, physical parameterisation schemes, land surface and wave model as the full-IFS. OpenIFS does not include any data assimilation routines but uses initial states generated beforehand with full-IFS. Therefore, OpenIFS has identical forecasting capability compared to corresponding IFS version.

Two versions of OpenIFS are used in this thesis. **Papers I, II and IV** use cycle 40R1 that was operational from November 2013 to May 2015 (ECMWF, 2023). **Paper III** uses cycle 43R3 that was operational between July 2017 and June 2018 (ECMWF, 2023).

2.2 Overview of the key parameterisations

The most important uncertain parameters belong to Stochastically Perturbed Parameters (SPP) scheme that is one option for representing the model uncertainty in ensemble forecasting. In SPP, the closure parameters are perturbed individually using coherent evolving random number fields. However, this thesis and especially **Paper III** focus on finding optimal deterministic values for the parameters. SPP scheme of model version 43R3 contains 20 parameters that are both instrumental for predictive skill and are difficult to determine exactly at the same time. A detailed description about SPP in IFS/OpenIFS is given in (Ollinaho et al., 2017). Table 1 gives an overview of the

parameterisation schemes and model parameters therein. These parameters are supposed to be used universally across all model resolutions. The scale-aware features have been taken into account already in the design of the parameterisation schemes. Therefore, these parameter values visible to the outside should, in theory, work for all available IFS/OpenIFS resolutions (ECMWF, 2017). The key parameters belong to the following sub-grid scale physical parameterisation schemes: turbulent diffusion and subgrid orography, convection, clouds and large-scale precipitation, and radiation. More details and descriptions how these parameters affect the model state are given below.

2.2.1 Turbulent diffusion and subgrid orography

The parameterisation scheme of turbulence contains parameterisations for surface drag and turbulent orographic form drag. Representation of the surface layer is based on the Monin-Obukhov similarity theory (Monin and Obukhov, 1954). The prognostic equation for wind speed U_n in IFS/OpenIFS is written as

$$\frac{\partial U_n}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\rho K \frac{\partial U_n}{\partial z} - M(U_n^u - \overline{U_n})) = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial J_m}{\partial z} \quad (7)$$

where ρ is density of air, K the eddy viscosity coefficient and $M(U_n^u - \overline{U_n})$ is mass flux of the strongest updraughts. The surface momentum flux J_m can be written as

$$J_m = \rho C_m |U_n|^2 \quad (8)$$

where C_m is the drag coefficient corresponding to CFM_OC and CFM_LA parameters and U_n is the wind speed. Modification of CFM_OC and CFM_LA affects the surface momentum flux, which means that they have a strong effect on wind speed at low levels above the surface. Increasing these parameters slows down the wind speed near the surface.

Turbulent orographic form drag scheme accounts for surface drag exerted by subgrid-scale mountains. The stress caused by orography can be written as

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial t} = -\alpha_{tofd} \beta_{tofd} C_{md} C_{corr} |U(z)| U(z) 2.109 e^{-(z/1500)^{1.5}} a_1 z^{-1.2} \quad (9)$$

where α_{tofd} is TOFDC parameter in Table 1, and in the default model it has value of 35. β_{tofd} , C_{md} and C_{corr} are other scaling and correction parameters. α_{tofd} is used to

parameterisation scheme	Parameter name	Short explanation
Turbulent diffusion and subgrid orography	CFM_OC	turbulent momentum transport to the surface over oceans
	CFM_LA	turbulent momentum transport to the surface over land
	TOFDC	turbulent orographic form drag
	HSDT	standard deviation of sub grid-scale orography
	VDEXC_LEN	length scale for vertical mixing in stable boundary layer
	ENTRORG	entrainment rate of deep organised convection
	ENTSHALP	enhanced entrainment rate for shallow (<200 hPa) convection
	DETRPEN	detrainment rate of penetrative convection
	RPRCON	convective cloud water/ice conversion to rain/snow
	CUDU	convective vertical momentum transport in x-direction
CUDV	convective vertical momentum transport in y-direction	
RTAU	timescale for CAPE consumption	
Clouds and large-scale precipitation	RAMID	relative humidity threshold for stratiform cloud formation
	RCLDIFF	diffusion coefficient for evaporation in turbulent mixing
	RCLCRIT	cloud water threshold for onset of stratiform precipitation
	RLCRITSNOW	threshold for snow autoconversion
Radiation	ZDECORR	vertical decorrelation distance of clouds
	ZSIQCW	standard deviation of horizontal distribution of cloud water
	ZRADEFF	effective radius of cloud water and ice particles
	ZHS_VDAERO	scale height of aerosol normal vertical distribution
	DELTA_AERO	aerosol optical thickness

Table 1: Short explanations of the parameters belonging to the SPP scheme. Parameters are divided by parameterisation schemes: turbulent diffusion and subgrid orography, convection, cloud and large-scale precipitation, and radiation (from Ollinaho et al., 2017).

modify how much the subgrid-scale mountains cause surface drag. Because mountains can reach relatively high altitude, the effect extends higher in the model in mountainous areas. a_1 is written as

$$a_1 = 1.427 \cdot 10^{-6} \sigma_{flt}^2 \quad (10)$$

where σ_{flt} is HSDT in Table 1. Modifying HSDT means modifying the height of subgrid-scale mountains and the amount of drag generated by the turbulent orographic form drag scheme. Increasing either α_{tofd} or σ_{flt} would lead to slower wind speeds in areas of complex orography.

In case of stable surface layer, the mixing length l or VDEXC_LEN in Table 1 is defined as

$$\frac{1}{l} = \frac{1}{\kappa z} + \frac{1}{\lambda} \quad (11)$$

where $\kappa = 0.4$ is the von Karman's constant and λ is the asymptotic length scale. This parameterisation determines how large the eddies are in the boundary layer. Therefore, VDEXC_LEN controls how efficiently the upper levels are coupled to the surface layer in stable boundary layer. Increasing VDEXC_LEN would mean that the surface drag is felt higher.

2.2.2 Convection

Convection is parametrised using a bulk mass flux scheme, in which updraughts in IFS are assumed to be in a steady state. For momentum, the scheme can be formulated as

$$-g \frac{\partial M_{up}}{\partial p} = E_{up} - D_{up} \quad (12)$$

and generally for any quantity ϕ carried with the flow

$$-g \frac{\partial (M_{up} \phi_{up})}{\partial p} = E_{up} \bar{\phi} - D_{up} \phi_{up} + O \quad (13)$$

where M_{up} refers to updraught mass flux, $\bar{\phi}$ is the large-scale mean value of ϕ and O refers to other terms (see Eq. 6.3 in ECMWF, 2017). Entrainment E_{up} and detrainment D_{up} for deep convection can be written as

$$E_{up} = \epsilon_{up} f \epsilon \frac{M_{up}}{\bar{\rho}} (1.3 - RH) \left(\frac{q_{sat}(\bar{T})}{q_{sat}(\bar{T}_{base})} \right)^3 \quad (14)$$

and

$$D_{up} = \delta_{up} \frac{M_{up}}{\bar{\rho}} (1.6 - RH) \quad (15)$$

where RH is the relative humidity q_{sat} is the specific humidity at saturation, \bar{T} is the large-scale average temperature and $\overline{T_{base}}$ is the average temperature at cloud base. $\epsilon_{up} = 1.75 \cdot 10^{-3} m^{-1}$ corresponds to ENTRORG, $f_\epsilon = 2.0$ corresponds to ENTSHALP and $\delta_{up} = 0.75 \cdot 10^{-4} m^{-1}$ to DETRPEN in Table 1. f_ϵ is used only if convection covers less than 200 hPa deep layer. In case of shallow convection, detrainment is

$$D_{up}^s = E_{up}^s (1.6 - RH) \quad (16)$$

Increasing any of these three parameters would mean that convective air and environmental air mix more efficiently. Mixing leads to convective updraughts becoming more diluted.

The rate of consumption of convective available potential energy (CAPE) by convection is defined as

$$\frac{\partial PCAPE}{\partial t} = - \frac{PCAPE - PCAPE_{bl}}{\tau} \quad (17)$$

where $PCAPE$ refers to CAPE of an entraining ascending air parcel and $PCAPE_{bl}$ to a reference value. τ corresponds to RTAU in Table 1, and it is the convective adjustment time scale that determines how fast convection is using the CAPE. Increasing RTAU means that convection consumes CAPE slower.

Conversion of cloud water and ice to rain and snow is formulated as

$$G = \frac{M_{up} c_0 (1.3\alpha_T + (1 - \alpha_T))}{\bar{\rho} 0.75 w_{up}} l_{up} (1 - e^{-(l_{up}/l_{crit})^2}) \quad (18)$$

where w_{up} is the updraught vertical velocity, l_{up} is the cloud water/ice content in the updraught, $l_{crit} = 0.5 g k g^{-1}$ a reference value and α_T is interpolation coefficient between the liquid and ice phase as function of temperature. $c_0 = 1.4 \cdot 10^{-3} s^{-1}$ corresponds RPRCON in Table 1. RPRCON controls how efficiently convection converts cloud water/ice to precipitation. For example increasing RPRCON would lead convective clouds precipitating faster, thus leading to drier troposphere.

Convection transports air parcels between atmospheric layers having different velocities. This in turn causes vertical transport of horizontal momentum and dissipation of kinetic energy. This can be written approximately as

$$-\left(\frac{\partial E_{kin}}{\partial t}\right) = \int_{P_{surf}}^0 (\bar{u}(f_u \frac{\partial u}{\partial t}) + \bar{v}(f_v \frac{\partial v}{\partial t})) \frac{dp}{g} \quad (19)$$

where f_u and f_v correspond to CUDU and CUDV in Table 1. f_u and f_v serve as multiplicative tuning parameters for the wind tendencies of the entire convection scheme. However, f_u and f_v are treated as one parameter in the tuning experiments, since treating the directions separately would be grossly nonphysical.

2.2.3 Clouds and large-scale precipitation

In the cloud scheme the threshold for formation of new stratiform clouds is defined as

$$RH_{crit} = RH_c + (1 - RH_c) \left(\frac{\sigma - \sigma_1}{1 - \sigma_1} \right)^2 \quad \sigma > \sigma_1 \quad (20)$$

$$RH_{crit} = RH_c \quad \sigma < \sigma_1 \quad (21)$$

where $\sigma = p/p_{surf}$ with p being the pressure and p_{surf} the surface pressure, and $\sigma_1 = 0.8$ is a reference value. $RH_c = 0.8$ corresponds RAMID in Table 1, and it is a parameter that controls how high the relative humidity must be in order to form new clouds. For example increasing RH_c would decrease the formation of clouds unless the moisture content of the air is increased.

The rate of generation of precipitation due to autoconversion of cloud water is parametrised as

$$S_{rain} = a c_0^* q_l^{cld} (1 + b_1 \sqrt{P_{loc}}) \left(1 - e^{-\left(\frac{q_l^{cld}}{q_l^{crit*} / (1 + b_1 \sqrt{P_{loc}})} \right)^2} \right) \quad (22)$$

and for ice as

$$S_{snow} = a 10^{-3} e^{0.03(T-273.15)} q_i^{cld} \left(1 - e^{-\left(\frac{q_i^{cld}}{q_i^{crit*} / (1 + b_1 \sqrt{P_{loc}})} \right)^2} \right) \quad (23)$$

where a is the fraction of grid box covered by clouds (0-1). $b_1 = 100(kgm^{-2}s^{-1})^{-0.5}$ and $c_0^* = 1.67 \cdot 10^{-4}s^{-1}$ are constants related to a characteristic time scale for conversion of cloud liquid droplets into rain drops, P_{loc} is the local cloudy precipitation rate, q_l^{cld} is the cloud liquid water content and q_i^{cld} is the cloud ice water content. q_l^{crit*} is the critical liquid water content, and q_i^{crit} is the critical ice water content. q_l^{crit*} and q_i^{crit} correspond to RCLCRIT and RLCRITSNOW in Table 1 respectively. q_l^{crit*} has the default value of $0.25gkg^{-1}$ over ocean and $0.55gkg^{-1}$ over land. The default value of q_i^{crit} is set to $3 \cdot 10^{-5}gkg^{-1}$. For example increasing the reference value q_l^{crit*} or q_i^{crit} would mean that the precipitation generation slows down, and cloud liquid water/ice content stays higher.

The rate of change of mass of raindrops is parametrised as

$$\frac{dm}{dt} = \frac{4\pi C(S_w - 1)(0.78 + 0.31S_c^{1/3}R_e^{1/2})}{A'' + B''} \quad (24)$$

where C is the capacitance of a spherical particle, $S_w = e/e_{sw}$ is the saturation ratio with respect to water, $S_c = 0.6$ is the Schmidt number and R_e the Reynolds number. Terms A'' and B'' represent heat conduction and vapour diffusion respectively

$$A'' = \frac{L}{K_a T} \left(\frac{L}{R_v T} - 1 \right), \quad B'' = \frac{R_v T}{\chi e_{sw}} \quad (25)$$

where L is the latent heat of vaporisation, K_a is the conductivity of air, T is the air temperature, R_v is the gas constant for water vapour and e_{sw} is the water vapour pressure at saturation. $\chi = 3.0 \cdot 10^{-6} s^{-1}$ is the diffusivity of water vapour in air corresponding to RCLDIFF in Table 1. Increasing χ would lead to term B'' being smaller and evaporation of raindrops being faster, so smaller portion of precipitation would reach the surface.

2.2.4 Radiation

The radiation transfer in IFS/OpenIFS is computed with the Monte Carlo Independent Column Approximation (McICA) algorithm. McICA sub-divides an area into columns, in which each model level can only have a cloud fraction of 0 or 1. Together with information about cloud fraction and cloud water content from the cloud scheme, McICA process is run N times to generate representations of vertical distribution of partial cloudiness. The degree of vertical stacking of the clouds in McICA is determined by the vertical decorrelation height ZDECORR in kilometres

$$\delta = 0.75 + 2.149 \cos(\phi) \text{ km} \quad (26)$$

where ϕ is the latitude. Increasing δ would mean that the clouds become vertically more overlapping. Stacking the clouds vertically in turn leads to more cloud-free areas and more solar shortwave radiation reaching the ground and more longwave radiation escaping from low atmospheric levels. Therefore, increasing δ acts to increase the amplitude of the daily temperature cycle.

Cloud layers have subgrid-scale inhomogeneity in horizontal distribution of cloud water. The radiation scheme includes a multiplicative tuning parameter ZSIGQCW that can

be used to modify the subgrid cloud water standard deviation coming from the cloud scheme. The default value of ZSIGQCW is 1.0. Increasing ZSIGQCW would mean that in optically thick parts of the cloud decks become even thicker and optically less thick areas become more transparent. Making optically thick areas even thicker does not modify the transfer of radiation much but making relatively transparent areas more transparent increases the amount of shortwave radiation reaching the ground and longwave radiation leaving the low levels. Therefore, increasing ZSIGQCW should have similar effect to increasing ZDECORR.

The number concentration of cloud droplets is bound by cloud water content and effective radius of cloud water and ice particles (ZRADEFF). The parameterisation follows Martin et al. (1994)

$$r_e = \left(\frac{3L}{4\pi\rho_w k N_{tot}} \right)^{1/3} \quad (27)$$

where L is the cloud water content, k is the relation between mean volume radius and effective radius, ρ_w is the density of water and N_{tot} is the particle number concentration. Increasing ZRADEFF would mean that the cloud contains fewer but larger particles. This in turn decreases the optical thickness so that more radiation can pass through. Therefore increasing ZRADEFF leads to amplification of daily temperature cycle.

The aerosol climatology used in OpenIFS/IFS has been produced by Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Service (Bozzo et al., 2017). Only the first degree impact on radiation transfer is taken into account, so for example interaction with clouds is ignored. Aerosol optical thickness height DELTA_AERO is defined as climatological two-dimensional field. Contribution to aerosol optical thickness mainly originates from sea-salt, mineral dust, organic carbon, black carbon and sulfates. Besides, tropospheric and stratospheric background aerosols are included. Aerosols mostly act to absorb and reflect solar radiation. Aerosols tend to warm middle and upper troposphere due to absorption and cool lower troposphere due to decreased flux of solar radiation. Therefore, increasing DELTA_AERO would increase the reflectance and absorption of solar radiation. This would lead to amplified warming of middle and upper troposphere and cooling of lower troposphere.

ZHS_VDAERO controls how the aerosols are distributed in the atmosphere. In the source regions, the aerosol distribution is limited to low levels meaning that the scale height of the aerosols is small. In advection areas, the aerosol distribution extends higher in the atmosphere, so the scale height is larger. Depending on the aerosol

species and location, the scale height typically ranges from hundreds of metres to a few kilometres. The scale height is also a climatological two-dimensional field. Increasing ZHS.VDAERO would mean that the aerosols reach higher in the atmosphere. The main implication is that the warmed and cooled layers move slightly upwards in the troposphere.

3 Methods and other materials

3.1 Data

This section explains all external datasets used in this thesis consisting of OpenIFS initial states, operational analyses and observations used in forecast verification.

3.1.1 Initial states

Two different OpenIFS initial state datasets are used. The first dataset called OpenEnsemble 1.0 covers a one-year period from 1 December 2016 to 30 November 2017. The initial states have been generated closely following what is done in the ECMWF operational ensemble using IFS cycle 43R3. This dataset contains twice-a-day (0000 UTC and 1200 UTC) initial states for 50 ensemble members and a control member for three OpenIFS resolutions: T_L159 (~ 120 km), T_L399 (~ 50 km) and T_L639 (~ 32 km). Singular vector (SV) and ensemble of data assimilations (EDA) perturbations are included in the dataset as separate files. It is possible to use only SV or EDA perturbations or to modify their amplitudes. This dataset is used to generate the forecasts in **Paper I**, to carry out the algorithmic optimisation in **Papers II** and **III**, and to generate the forecasts and model counterparts in **Paper IV**.

The other initial state dataset covers a one-year period from 1 December 2017 to 30 November 2018 using IFS cycle 43R3. This dataset contains a deterministic T_L399 and T_L639 initial state once a week at 0000 UTC. These initial states are used to generate an independent set of forecasts used in verification of the optimised model versions in **Paper III**.

3.1.2 Analyses for verification

Operational analyses are used in the verification of forecasts in **Paper I** and in the verification of optimised model versions in **Paper III**. The analyses are generated at ECMWF and downloaded from the ECMWF meteorological archive. **Paper I** is using operational analyses for the same time period as OpenEnsemble 1.0 (Dec 2016 to Nov 2017). During this time two different IFS versions were operational: cycle 43R1 until July 2017 and cycle 43R3 after that. **Paper III** is using operational analyses for 1 Dec 2017 to 10 Dec 2018. During that time two IFS cycles were operational as well: cycle 43R3 until June 2018 and cycle 45R1 after that.

Analysis states used during the model optimisation in **Paper III** are generated from the unperturbed initial states of OpenEnsemble 1.0.

3.1.3 Observations

Paper IV uses observations as the reference in forecast verification. The observations consist of conventional radio soundings and AMSU-A channel 5 brightness temperature measurements. The radio soundings are global TEMP observations launched at 0000 UTC and 1200 UTC. The satellite data consists of measurements from AMSU-A channel 5 at observation times of 0000 UTC \pm 30 minutes and 1200 UTC \pm 30 minutes. The radio soundings are interpolated to 200, 500 and 850 hPa levels as only these levels are available in the OpenIFS forecast data used, and for simplicity the soundings are assumed to represent columns above the launching sites. The observation errors are treated in the same way. When comparing the model data against the radio soundings, the gridded model data is interpolated linearly in the horizontal plane to the observation points.

AMSU-A channel 5 consists of two frequency bands at 53.596 ± 0.115 GHz that are primarily sensitive to middle-tropospheric temperature but channel 5 is also slightly sensitive to tropospheric hydrometeors and surface temperature. More details of AMSU-A can be found for example in Geer et al. (2012) and Bormann and Bauer (2010).

3.2 Ensemble forecasting

OpenEPS facilitates running OpenIFS forecasts in all papers. OpenEPS is a light-weight workflow manager for running ensemble forecasts for research purposes. OpenEPS enables running ensembles with different numerical models (in this thesis, OpenIFS), and to set up post-processing methods and optimisation algorithms, such as EPPES, to be a part of the workflow. As OpenEPS manages the workflow, the user only needs to define experimental setting, such as model configuration, ensemble size, and how often the ensembles are launched. When running an optimisation algorithm, definition of the cost function and instructions how it should be calculated are required. For a more detailed description of OpenEPS and how to set up experiments, see **Paper I**.

3.3 Algorithmic tuning method

3.3.1 Optimisation algorithms

Two algorithms are used for optimising model parameters in this thesis. **Paper II** uses Ensemble prediction and parameter estimation system (EPPES, Järvinen et al., 2012; Laine et al., 2012) and Differential evolution (DE, Storn and Price, 1997; Shemyakin and Haario, 2018). EPPES is a fully nonlinear parameter estimation method. It is a hierarchical statistical method that uses Gaussian proposal distributions, importance sampling, and sequential modeling for optimising model parameters and their uncertainties while running ensembles of short initialised forecasts.

The basic idea of EPPES is the following: The algorithm samples an ensemble of parameter vectors, one for each ensemble member, from a prior distribution based on the hyper-parameters of the method. Then, an ensemble of forecasts is run with the perturbed parameters. For each parameter vector, a cost function is evaluated using the forecast and a reference (e.g., analysis or observation). Based on the cost function values, the algorithm calculates importance weights, which are used to update the hyper-parameters for subsequent resampling. The process continues until a stopping criterion (e.g., number of algorithm steps) is reached. A detailed application example can be found from, e.g., Ollinaho et al. (2013).

DE is heuristically based on natural selection. It consists of evolving population of

parameter vectors where vectors leading to good cost function values thrive and produce an offspring, while vectors leading to bad cost function values are eliminated.

3.3.2 Optimisation targets

Optimisation of a model requires some way to measure distance to a reference state. Target of the optimisation is to minimise that measure. Moist total energy norm (ΔE_m see, e.g., Ehrendorfer et al., 1999) is used as the cost function in **Papers II** and **III**. It is a comprehensive multivariate integral over the entire model domain. ΔE_m is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E_m = & \frac{1}{2M_a} \int_{\eta} \int_D \left(u'^2 + v'^2 + \frac{c_p}{T_r} T'^2 + c_q \frac{L^2}{c_p T_r} q'^2 \right) dD d\eta \\ & + \frac{1}{2A} \int_D \left(R \frac{T_r}{p_r} \log p'_s \right) dD, \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

where u' , v' , T' , q' , p'_s are the differences between the forecast and the reference state for u and v wind components, temperature, specific humidity, and surface pressure. c_p is the specific heat capacity at constant pressure, L the vaporisation energy of water, M_a the total mass of the atmosphere, and A surface area of the Earth. T_r and p_r are reference values for temperature and pressure. T_r is set to 280 K and p_r to 1000 hPa. c_q is a scaling constant set to unity. The integrals are over the horizontal D and vertical η domains (Ollinaho et al., 2014). The moist total energy norm essentially tells how far two atmospheric states are from each another in energy units. This formulation of the cost function assumes that the analyses represent the real world observations well. However, in reality, the analyses can have biases as well, and grid-form representation can treat small-scale features poorly.

For illustrative purposes **Paper II** also uses the global root mean squared error of 850 hPa geopotential height (ΔZ):

$$\Delta Z = \sqrt{\frac{1}{D} \int_D (Z_{850} - Z'_{850})^2 dD} \quad (29)$$

where Z_{850} and Z'_{850} denote 850 hPa geopotential in the reference state and perturbed forecast at each grid point. D denotes the horizontal domain. This is a restrictive cost function formulation expected to perform poorly due to insufficient exploitation of information of the model state, aggressive interpolation and ambiguity in locations where 850 hPa level is below ground.

3.4 Measuring the parameter convergence

Regular continuous ranked probability score (CRPS) is written in kernel form (Gneiting and Raftery, 2007) as:

$$CRPS = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{j=1}^M |x_j - y| - \frac{1}{2M^2} \sum_{j=1}^M \sum_{k=1}^M |x_j - x_k| \quad (30)$$

where x_j and x_k are ensemble members, y is reference quantity (e.g. observation or analysis) and M is the size of the ensemble. CRPS is used in forecast verification in **Paper I**.

Ferro et al. (2008) derives a fair version of the CRPS (fCRPS), and Leutbecher (2018) writes it in kernel form as:

$$fCRPS = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{j=1}^M |x_j - y| - \frac{1}{2M(M-1)} \sum_{j=1}^M \sum_{k=1}^M |x_j - x_k| \quad (31)$$

fCRPS is used in **Paper I** to verify the ensemble forecasts and in **Paper II** to measure parameter convergence. However, fCRPS is more convenient to use in parameter convergence testing if it is split into two parts and used as:

$$fCRPS_1 = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{j=1}^M |\theta'_{j,n} - \theta_{d,n}| \quad (32a)$$

$$fCRPS_2 = \frac{1}{2M(M-1)} \sum_{j=1}^M \sum_{k=1}^M |\theta'_{j,n} - \theta'_{k,n}| \quad (32b)$$

where n is the index over tunable parameters, $\theta_{j,n}$ and $\theta_{k,n}$ are the parameter values used by ensemble members j and k , $\theta_{d,n}$ is the default parameter value, and M is the ensemble size. Here $fCRPS_1$ measures the convergence of parameter mean value and $fCRPS_2$ convergence of parameter uncertainty. The property of fairness ensures that the scores are directly comparable between ensemble forecasts or optimisation experiments using different ensemble sizes.

3.5 Forecast verification

A number of different forecast verification methods are used in this thesis. Root mean squared error (RMSE) is used in **Paper III** for verification of the optimised model versions.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{D} \int_D (y - x)^2 dD} \quad (33)$$

where y is the analysis, x is the corresponding forecast and D refers to integration over the horizontal domain, The RMSE values are collated into scorecards respect to the control model version showing the impact of model tuning. Ensemble mean RMSE used in **Paper IV** is instead:

$$RMSE_{ens} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{D} \int_D (y - \bar{x})^2 - \sigma_o^2 - \sigma_x^2 dD}, \quad (34)$$

where \bar{x} is the ensemble mean forecast, σ_x^2 the ensemble variance, and σ_o^2 the error variance of the observations. **Paper IV** uses the ensemble mean RMSE to visualise the spread-skill relationship.

Besides ensemble mean RMSE (Eq. 34), **Paper IV** demonstrates verification of ensemble forecasts with Dawid-Sebastiani score (DSS), and most importantly, with the filter likelihood score (FLS). Dawid-Sebastiani score (DSS, Dawid and Sebastiani, 1999) comes from the ignorance score of a Gaussian distribution with ensemble mean \bar{z} and ensemble standard deviation σ_z . Following Eq. 6.10 in (Vannitsem et al., 2018) and assuming the observations uncorrelated, the univariate form of DSS can be written as

$$DSS = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{i=1}^L \left(\frac{(y_i - \bar{x}_i)^2}{\sigma_{x,i}^2} + \log \sigma_{x,i}^2 \right), \quad (35)$$

where L is the number of observations, y_i the observed value, \bar{x}_i the ensemble mean, and $\sigma_{x,i}$ the ensemble spread corresponding to observation i . FLS can be seen to originate from the Kalman filter theory (Schweppe, 1965). Unlike DSS, FLS takes the observation uncertainty into account as well. Even though the origins of DSS and FLS are different, the only difference between them is the treatment of observation uncertainty. FLS can be written in the same form as DSS above assuming uncorrelated observations:

$$FLS = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{i=1}^L \left[\frac{(y_i - \bar{x}_i)^2}{\sigma_{o,i}^2 + \sigma_{x,i}^2} + \log(\sigma_{o,i}^2 + \sigma_{x,i}^2) \right], \quad (36)$$

where $\sigma_{o,i}$ is the observation error of observation i .

4 Experimental set-ups

Paper I uses initial states of OpenEnsemble 1.0 to run ensemble forecasts every 8th day beginning from 1 Dec 2016 totaling to 46 initial dates using all available resolutions. The ensemble size varies between 8 and 50 but the forecast range is 10 days. These experiments contain ensemble forecasts with only SV perturbations active, EDA active and both active. There are also experiments with the perturbations multiplied by 1.2. The full array of experiments of **Paper I** is shown in Table 2.

Name	Ens size	Dates	Notes
T _L 159-SV	50	46	SV pert only
T _L 159-EDA	50	46	EDA pert only
T _L 159-BOTH	50	46	EDA and SV pert
T _L 159-SV+	8	46	SV pert multiplied by 1.2
T _L 159-EDA+	8	46	EDA pert multiplied by 1.2
T _L 159-BOTH+	8	46	EDA and SV pert multiplied individually by 1.2
T _L 399-SV	20	46	SV pert only
T _L 399-EDA	20	46	EDA pert only
T _L 399-BOTH	50	46	EDA and SV pert
T _L 639-SV	20	46	SV pert only
T _L 639-EDA	20	46	EDA pert only
T _L 639-BOTH	20	46	EDA and SV pert

Table 2: Experiments conducted for **Paper I**. Experiment name includes the used resolution as well as the type of initial state perturbations used. Ensemble size, the number of ensemble initialisation dates and finally notes regarding the experiment.

These experiments are then verified with ensemble mean RMSE (Eq. 34, with $\sigma_o = 0$) and spread, regular CRPS (Eq. 30) and fCRPS (Eq. 31).

Papers II and **III** focus on optimisation of OpenIFS parameters. **Paper II** tests how different choices affect the optimisation process itself. The test set-up is fully controlled and known because the reference data used as the truth is generated with control model having the default parameter values. In order to separate these semi-realistic tests from fully-realistic optimisation, term 'parameter convergence test' is coined. An array of convergence tests are run using different levels of realism (Table 3). The parameters used in **Paper II** belonging to the convection scheme of OpenIFS are shown in Table 4. Parameters θ_1 and θ_2 are selected for more in-depth inspection about optimal forecast range and ensemble size. Another array of convergence tests

with various forecast ranges and ensemble sizes are run using both EPPES and DE as the optimisation algorithm, and the parameter convergence is measured with the fCRPS components (Eq. 32).

	Number of parameters	Different states	initial	Stochastic (SPPT)	physics
Level 0 (L0)	2	No		No	
Level 1 (L1)	2	Yes		No	
Level 2 (L2)	2	Yes		Yes	
Level 3 (L3)	5	Yes		Yes	

Table 3: Summary of convergence tests with different degrees of realism.

Parameter	Default value	Short description
ENTSHALP (θ_1)	2.0	Entrainment rate scaling factor for shallow convection
ENTRORG (θ_2)	$1.75 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}^{-1}$	Entrainment per unit length for deep convection
DETRPEN (θ_3)	$0.75 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}^{-1}$	Turbulent detrainment per unit length for deep convection
RPRCON (θ_4)	$1.4 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$	Conversion factor from cloud water/ice to rain/snow
RDEPTH5 (θ_5)	20000 Pa	Depth of layer for shallow convection
RMFDEPS (θ_6)	0.3	Fractional massflux for downdraughts at level of free sinking
RHEBC (θ_7)	0.9	Critical relative humidity below cloud for evaporation
ENTRDD (θ_8)	$3.0 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}^{-1}$	Average entrainment per unit length for downdraughts

Table 4: Parameters of the convection scheme of OpenIFS. θ_1 and θ_2 are used the most in **Paper II**.

Paper III extends the work of **Paper II** by presenting examples of fully-realistic optimisation of 19 (20) parameters belonging to the stochastically perturbed parameters (SPP) scheme (Ollinaho et al., 2017) of OpenIFS. There are two important notes about using the parameters of SPP (Table 1) in the tuning experiments. Firstly, turbulent momentum transfer to the surface is defined separately for ocean (CFM_OC) and land areas (CFM_LA) in SPP, but it is treated as one parameter (CFM), except for experiment four (see details below). Secondly, convective momentum transport caused by zonal wind (CUDU) and meridional wind (CUDV) are treated as one parameter (CUDUDV), because it is not physically meaningful to treat the directions separately.

In order to facilitate the application of algorithmic tuning, the parameter values are normalised according to

$$X_n = \frac{X}{X_0} \quad (37)$$

where X is the actual parameter value and X_0 is the parameter default value. There are two practical reasons for using normalised parameter values instead of their actual values. Firstly, the convergence testing in **Paper II** showed that EPPES does not work very well if the values of the parameters differ several orders of magnitude from each other, and secondly, some of the parameters are actually two-dimensional climatological fields or other two or three-dimensional quantities inside the model. Normalisation to unity enables treating all the parameters in the same way.

The details of the tuning experiments carried out for **Paper III** are presented below. The first experiment (E_{def}) mimics an optimisation experiment spanning over three years. However, the ensemble initial states of OpenEnsemble 1.0 span over one year only, so the same year is used three times but selecting different initialisation dates each time. Thus, the 'first' year starts from 1 Dec 2016 00 UTC, and ensembles are launched every three days until the end of data set, then continuing for the 'second' year starting from 2 Dec 2016 00 UTC, and again to the 'third' year starting from 3 Dec 2016 00 UTC. The other experiments ($E1$ to $E3$ and E_{CFM}) are one-year experiments starting from 1 Dec 2016 00 UTC, and they use initial states every three days. The experimental set-up for the algorithm is based on the results of **Paper II**, and consists of 20-member 36-hour long ensemble forecasts with perturbed initial states and model parameters. The initial set-up of the parameter distributions in the five experiments is explained below:

- Default experiment (E_{def}): The initial value of the parameters are the default values of OpenIFS.
- Experiment 1 ($E1$): As in E_{def} since this is just the first year of E_{def} .
- Experiment 2 ($E2$): Half of the parameters have 5% higher values than the default, while the other parameters have 5% lower values than the default.
- Experiment 3 ($E3$): As $E2$, but with opposite signs.
- Experiment CFM (E_{CFM}): as $E1$, but with CFM parameter treated separately for ocean and land.

For all five experiments, the initial variance of the parameters is set to 0.1 corresponding to roughly 32% standard deviation. The main objective is to search for the

optimal mean value for these parameters, but the optimisation algorithm needs an initial estimate on how certain (or uncertain) the initial parameter value is. The initial uncertainty is set relatively high to allow EPPES to generously explore the parameter space but still limiting the potentially detrimental effects discovered in **Paper II**.

The tuned model versions are verified against operational analysis using an independent set of forecasts with resolutions of T_L399 (the same as in tuning) and higher resolution of T_L639 (~ 32 km). The verifying forecast set consists of 53 10-day forecasts launched on 1 Dec 2017 00UTC, 8 Dec 2017 00UTC, ... , 30 Nov 2018 00UTC.

Lastly, a simple parameter correlation search method using short tuning experiments is presented together with a comparison to correlations given by EPPES. 10 additional tuning experiments consisting of 53 algorithm steps are run. The short experiments are initialised as E_{def} but the initial parameter mean values are sampled randomly from uniform distribution of $[0.95, 1.05]$. Experiment E1 is also rerun without cost function ranking (called E_{norank} hereafter) in order to see if the ranking procedure has effect on the correlations.

Testing filter likelihood score in **Paper IV** is performed using two OpenIFS cy40r1 ensemble forecast datasets with resolution of T_L639 . Firstly, 10-day atmospheric forecasts for three different types of initial state perturbations are run: EDA only, SV only, and combined EDA and SV. In total 45 ensembles of 20 members are launched 8 days apart for dates between 1 Dec 2016 and 18 November 2017 (dataset 1). This ensemble set is used to compare different verification metrics and in calculating the filter likelihood score against sounding data. Secondly, in total 53 ensembles of 20 members are launched 7 days apart between December 1st 2016 and November 30th 2017 (dataset 2). These ensembles use both EDA and SV perturbations in the initial states, and have the stochastic model uncertainty component (SPPT) active as well. This ensemble data is used to calculate filter likelihood against AMSU-A channel 5 observations.

The scores are calculated separately for each forecast lead time (or over a time window of ± 30 for the satellite data) at 12-h interval up to 240 hours. The resulting values are further averaged over different observation locations (or the three geographical regions for the soundings) and the 45 and 53 ensemble runs in datasets (1) and (2), respectively. The scores are computed in observation space, so light interpolation of model fields to the sounding locations is performed but construction of model counterparts for

AMSU-A channel 5 requires specialised tools. Conversion of the model fields into brightness temperature in observation space is performed with Radiance Simulator software (NWP-SAF, 2022) that is a wrapper for the RTTOV library (Saunders et al., 2018). The computation of the scores is done separately for three regions: Northern extratropics ($> 20^{\circ}\text{N}$), Tropics (20°S - 20°N) and Southern extratropics ($> 20^{\circ}\text{S}$).

5 Summary of the results

5.1 Developing and testing the initial states and the ensemble workflow manager

Paper I introduces the dataset of initial states and the ensemble forecasting software OpenEPS. The initial states and the software are used to demonstrate various cases of academic ensemble forecasting and forecast verification in order to emphasise flexibility and versatility of the system.

The first test case demonstrates the basic comparison of ensemble root mean squared error (RMSE) and spread with different OpenIFS resolutions and ensemble initial state perturbation configurations. Theoretically increasing resolution should enhance the reliability of the ensemble forecasts, and the best initial state perturbation should be EDA+SV. This is exactly what is seen in Fig. 1 (a) and (b) that show how the lines are the closest to each other for the highest resolution. Also the effect of initial state perturbation configuration agrees with the theory. The most reliable ensemble forecasting system is the one with EDA and SV perturbations active. Panels (c) and (d) also demonstrate how ensemble mean on average outperforms the unperturbed control forecasts. When using EDA perturbations the ensemble spread tends to decrease during the early hours of the forecasts. **Paper I** concludes that this is caused by missing model uncertainty representation leading to imbalance of the initial state perturbations in the early hours.

The second test case is a comparison between the traditional CRPS (Eq. 30) and fair CRPS (fCRPS, Eq. 31) with different ensemble sizes, different resolutions and initial state perturbation configurations. Traditional CRPS is proportional to ensemble size so that the score becomes smaller as ensemble size grows. fCRPS instead has been designed so that it re-scales the score so that it corresponds to the score of an ensemble

of infinite size (Leutbecher, 2018). The initial state dataset and OpenEPS can be used to demonstrate that small ensembles lead to higher score than large ensembles when traditional CRPS is used and to the same score when fCRPS is used. fCRPS also clearly illustrates the impact of resolution and initial state perturbations. Firstly, higher resolution leads to lower fCRPS meaning better forecast performance. Secondly, the more comprehensive the initial state perturbations are, the better the forecast performance is. This is seen in Fig. 1 (e) and (f) as EDA+SV outperforms EDA and SV for all resolutions.

The third test case is a sensitivity test with SV and EDA perturbation magnitudes, which are tuning parameters of ensemble forecasting system. The magnitude of each initial state perturbation configuration (EDA, SV, EDA+SV) of resolution T_L159 were multiplied by 1.2. Multiplication of the initial state perturbations improves fCRPS for EDA, SV and EDA+SV respect to their control configurations (not shown). Potential for tuning ensemble prediction system encourages using the initial states and OpenEPS for tuning model closure parameters. This is discussed further in Sections 5.2 and 5.3, and in **Papers II** and **III**.

5.2 Optimising the parameter optimisation

The next step is to study how to exercise algorithmic optimisation of closure parameters in a computationally efficient manner. **Paper II** presents an in-depth analysis of different technical aspects related to algorithmic optimisation. The optimisation experiments in **Paper II** are limited to a semi-realistic framework meaning that the truth is always known. Tuning is performed against the default model instead of analyses, reanalyses or observations. Partial removal of unknowns gives an additional degree of control over the tuning process. Term 'convergence test' is used for optimisation experiment that uses artificially created truth as the reference.

Paper II investigates fast, efficient and economical tuning from four view-points: (1) which perturbations should be included in tuning? (2) What kind of optimisation target or cost function is most likely to work well? (3) What is most likely the most efficient tuning set-up in terms of forecast range and ensemble size? (4) What tuning set-up is the most reliable? The results are then boiled down to a recipe for efficient tuning. These aspects need to be studied in order to understand how to best tackle the challenge of fully-realistic optimisation of all key parameters at once in **Paper III**.

Figure 1: Ensemble root mean squared errors, ensemble spreads and fair CRPS with different model resolutions and initial state perturbation configurations. Adapted and modified from Figures 1, 2 and 4 of **Paper I**.

View-point (1) is investigated with convergence tests using different levels of complexity. Tests included a trivial test with only parameter perturbations, a test with ensemble initial state perturbations active, a test with initial state and model perturbations (SPPT) active and also a test with additional tuning parameters included. The main observations are that in the trivial test the parameters tend to converge towards point values. Instead in the rest of the tests some degree of uncertainty remains as the initial state and model perturbations prevent convergence to point values. Adding model perturbations and additional tuning parameters do not change the characteristics of the convergence, so initial state perturbations proved to be sufficient for preventing overconfident convergence. Initial state perturbations also increase the information input as the sample of weather states becomes more diversified.

View-point (2) is studied by comparing parameter convergence with a good cost function (moist total energy norm, ΔE_m , Eq. 28) to a bad cost function (root mean squared error of 850 hPa geopotential, ΔZ , Eq. 29). Fig. 2 shows that the good cost function ΔE_m leads to faster reduction of uncertainty than the bad cost function ΔZ . The reason why ΔE_m leads to faster convergence than ΔZ is that ΔE_m contains those atmospheric variables (wind, temperature, specific humidity and surface pressure) that are directly sensitive to the perturbations of the parameters of the convection scheme.

Figure 2: Parameter convergence of two parameters in convergence tests with two different cost functions. Panel (a) shows θ_1 (ENTSHALP) and panel (b) θ_2 (ENTRORG). The x-axes show the number of steps used and the y-axes show the parameter values. Continuous black lines show the parameter mean values (μ) and the dash-dotted lines show the uncertainty ($\mu \pm 2\sigma$) when ΔE_m is used. The cyan lines and shading on the background show the same for ΔZ . Both convergence tests use initial state perturbations, 50 member ensembles, 48 hour forecasts and EPPES as the optimiser. Adapted from Fig. 2 of **Paper II**.

The most important part of **Paper II** is related to view-point (3) that investigates the optimal combination of forecast range and ensemble size. An array of convergence tests with different forecast ranges and ensemble sizes is run and fCRPS components (Eq. 32) for parameter θ_2 shown in Fig. 3. Panel (a) shows that there is the most blue colour in the figure at forecast range of 24 h pointing out the most successful convergence. This means that the cost function ΔE_m is the most sensitive to the parameter perturbations at that range. However, panel (a) does not answer to what is the optimal ensemble size. Panel (b) shows the evolution of the 24 h convergence tests with different ensemble sizes. The strong progress towards better parameter values and smaller spread is seen for all ensemble sizes. The point, however, is that the rate of the parameter convergence is only weakly proportional to the ensemble size. This means that decreasing the ensemble size and reinvesting the saved resources to the number of algorithm steps has a positive impact on the outcome of algorithmic tuning. Based on Fig. 3 the optimal ensemble size is around 20 members. Smaller ensembles tend to lead to unstable convergence and larger ensembles to waste of computational resources.

Answering to view-point (4) revealed that a set-up leading to good convergence is likely reliable as well meaning that repetition of the convergence test yields similar results consistently. The reliability was tested running a series of L1 and L2 convergence tests (see Table 3) with the forecast range ensemble size combinations highlighted in Fig. 3 (a). In case of L1, both set-ups yielded consistently similar convergence but in case of L2, only the more optimal set-up performed consistently. This is an additional piece of evidence that forecast range of 24 hours and ensemble size of about 20 is the optimal choice.

A couple of pitfalls were encountered. The most notable one is that the optimal parameter values seem to depend on the forecast range (Fig. 4). Moreover, ensemble forecasts generated with optimised parameter values can lead to lower cost function values than ensemble forecasts with the default values even though control model with default parameter values serves as the reference (not shown). The only way to get this outcome is by inhibiting the growth of initial state (and model) perturbations with the optimised parameter values, and hence, decreasing the ensemble spread. Other pitfalls are of more technical nature. There seem to be no universal settings for the optimisation algorithms that would work well regardless of the optimisation set-up. Some settings work better for smaller ensembles and other for larger ensembles. Also starting too far away from the optimum may lead the parameter convergence to stick

Figure 3: Convergence of ENTRORG in convergence tests with various set-ups gauged with fCRPS components (Eq. 32). In panel (a) the x-axis shows the forecast length and the y-axis shows the ensemble size used in the convergence tests. Panel (b) shows evolution of the convergence tests using 24 hour forecast length therefore having the number of steps on the x-axis. The left-hand sides of the blocks represent the average distance of the parameter values from the default value and the right-hand sides represent the spreads of the parameter value distributions. The highlighted boxes mark the tests selected for the further study of reliability of the convergence. Adapted and modified from Figures 3 and 4 of **Paper II**.

to a local optimum along the way towards the global optimum.

The findings of **Paper II** can be summarised into a recipe for economical and efficient algorithmic tuning. (1) Use at least initial state perturbations (and possibly also model perturbations). (2) Use as comprehensive measure as the cost function as possible (suggestion: ΔE_m). (3) Use a relatively short forecast range (suggestion: 24 hours) and (4) use a relatively small ensemble size (suggestion: 20 members). The recipe was tested with additional convergence tests with five ($\theta_1 - \theta_5$) and eight parameters ($\theta_1 - \theta_8$ in Table 4) and in the most of the cases the outcome was positive. Especially in the eight-parameter test, all parameters showed convergence towards their default values. However, one parameter seemed to be insensitive as the uncertainty decreased only little.

Figure 4: Final mean values of θ_2 (ENTRORG) proposed by EPPES at the end of the convergence tests in Fig. 3 (a). Purple (green) colour means that the final mean value is above (below) the default value of $1.75 \cdot 10^{-3} m^{-1}$. Adapted and modified from Fig. 6 of **Paper II**.

5.3 Simultaneous parameter optimisation in practice

Papers I and **II** presented all preparatory work required to proceed to the most important part of this thesis that is **Paper III**, which investigates fully-realistic optimisation of all key parameters of OpenIFS simultaneously. The aim is to use the tools of **Paper I** and the knowledge of efficient parameter optimisation of **Paper II** in practise and optimise 19 (20) parameters belonging to the SPP scheme. **Paper III** shows that the recipe of **Paper II** works remarkably well but every tuning experiment ends up in different optimal parameter values. Besides the positive results, the shortcomings are also discussed.

Paper III begins with an overview of a long optimisation experiment mimicking a three-year and 365 steps long experiment. Fig. 5 presents the convergence of all parameters of SPP. Based on the figure, the identifiability and need for tuning varies between the parameters. Most of the parameters are well identifiable shown by convergence to very small range. However, there are still a number of not very well identifiable parameters that exhibit slow decrease of uncertainty. Fig. 5 shows that there are parameters that are likely to benefit from tuning as they converge relatively far away

from the default value.

Fig. 5 also gives indications of how long a tuning experiment is long enough. Most of the movement in the parameter mean values takes place early on in the tuning experiment and reduces greatly in about 50 algorithm steps. For many parameters the decrease of uncertainty slows down considerably after 100 steps. However, the decrease of uncertainty may resume again later in the experiment. Therefore, the length of the experiment depends on how confident outcome is required by the user. For the main experiments of **Paper III**, 122 steps (one year every three days) was deemed to be enough.

Another way to view the progress of tuning is to look at the cost function values. Fig. 6 shows the evolution of the moist total energy norm (ΔE_m) in the four main tuning experiments. In all four cases the tuning is progressing towards more optimal model since the cost function value decreases. Actually, the majority of the decrease already takes place during the first 30 steps, and after about 80 steps the cost function values stay flat. This an additional piece of evidence that the choice to use 122 steps in the main optimisation experiments is enough. At the end of the optimisation, all experiments have slightly lower cost function value than the control ensembles generated with the default parameter values. This means that the model has been optimised successfully. The fluctuation that remains near the end of the experiments is caused by natural variability in the predictability of the weather. Fig. 6 also shows that the initial parameter uncertainty was likely too large and included grossly nonphysical propositions. Actually there are ΔE_m values way outside the plot. However, Fig. 6 shows that EPPES is able to deal with bad parameter propositions. Furthermore, EPPES manages to rule out all bad options in less than 30 steps.

It is remarkable that the cost function values of the four tuning experiments in Fig. 6 are very close to each other but the final parameter mean values in Fig. 7 differ from each other substantially. Fig. 7 shows the initial parameter mean values, final mean values and remaining standard deviations for the default experiment E_{def} and four main optimisation experiments (E1 – E3 and E_{CFM}). The changes the parameter values experience are surprisingly large: up to 30%. The fact that the outcome of the tuning experiments varies without significant variation in the cost function value indicates that there are multiple local optima that minimise the cost function almost equally well. The parameter space can also be relatively flat in terms of cost function value.

Figure 5: Parameter convergence during a 365 steps long optimisation experiment E_{def} . Year 2017 is used for three times but so that different initialisation dates are used on each round. X-axis shows the running number of algorithm steps of EPPES and y-axis shows the relative parameter values. Parameter values assigned to individual ensemble members are shown with black dots, parameter mean value with a red line, parameter mean value ± 2 standard deviations with blue lines and the default parameter value with a green line. The vertical magenta lines point out the iteration number 122 that is the last iteration of the first year. Only every third parameter ensemble is displayed. Adapted from Fig. 1 of **Paper III**.

Figure 6: Evolution of the moist total energy norm (ΔE_m) in the four main tuning experiments. X-axis shows the iteration count during the experiments and y-axis shows the value of ΔE_m . In panels (a) to (d) the green dots show ΔE_m for individual ensemble members and red crosses show the ensemble mean. Panel (e) is a zoom-in to the last 10 steps in panels (a) to (d). Also control ensembles created with the default model are shown with cyan color. In panel (e) ensemble members are shown with dots and ensemble mean values as crosses. Adapted from Fig. 2 of **Paper III**.

Figure 7: Initial and final parameter values and remaining standard deviation of the parameter value distributions of the default experiment E_{def} and the four main experiments E_1 , E_2 , E_3 and E_{CFM} . The parameter names are shown between the initial and final values. The parameter values are shown with respect to the default values used in OpenIFS, thus being 1.0 for all parameters. Experiments E_{def} , E_1 and E_{CFM} begin from the default values whereas in case of E_2 and E_3 the initial values are either 1.05 or 0.95. In experiment E_{CFM} , CFM parameter is treated as two parameters separately for ocean and land areas. Initial variance of the parameters is 0.1 corresponding to standard deviation of about 0.32. Adapted from Fig. 3 of **Paper III**.

Optimised model versions E_{def} , $E_1 - E_3$ and E_{CFM} are verified with global root mean squared error (RMSE) using the independent dataset. The outcomes for $E_1 - E_3$ and E_{CFM} are shown as verification scorecards in Fig. 8. The scorecards show RMSE values as relative change with respect to the default model. A negative value implies a gain in forecast skill relative to the default model. Instead, positive values imply loss in forecast skill. The verification reveals two types of optimal models. The first type represented by E_1 , E_2 and E_3 is characterised by a strong gain in forecast performance especially in wind components and specific humidity. However, the gains come with the cost of degrading geopotential. The other type, represented by E_{CFM} , is characterised by slight gains in skill in most aspects, except for specific humidity at 850 hPa near the forecast range of 36 hours and weaker improvement of the wind components throughout the forecast range.

Figure 8: Verification of the four tuning experiments using global root mean squared error scorecards respect to the default model. X-axis of each panel shows the forecast range in hours and y-axis shows the atmospheric variables used. Z is geopotential, U and V are the zonal and meridional components of wind, T is temperature and Q is specific humidity. Z, U, V, T and Q are verified at six pressure levels from top down: 100, 250, 500, 700, 850 and 1000 hPa. The two-dimensional variables at the bottom of the panels are two-metre temperature (t2m), mean sea level pressure (mslp), ten-metre zonal wind (u10m), ten-metre meridional wind (v10m), total cloud cover (tcc), low cloud cover (lcc), medium cloud cover (mcc), high cloud cover (hcc) and total column of water vapour (tcwv). Blue colour means that the optimised model outperforms the default model. Black dots indicate that the difference between the optimised and control model is statistically significant at 95% level according to two-sample t-test. Geopotential data at 100 and 250 hPa is missing due to missing operational data. Adapted from Fig. 4 of **Paper III**.

E1 appears to be the best of these four optimised model versions. It has relatively little degrading features, and the skill degradation is not statistically significant except for 10 metre u-wind at 12 hours. The average overall RMSE reduction is -0.65%. Respective change for E2 is -0.36%, for E3 -0.32% and for E_{CFM} -0.44%. E_{def} (i.e. E1 extended for another 243 steps) of Fig 5 was also verified. The result is very similar compared to E1. Average of the RMSE reduction is -0.66%. Thus, the parameters do not improve much during the last 243 steps supporting the conclusion that $O(100)$ steps is sufficient for parameter convergence, unless new training material with more atmospheric variability is introduced.

Contribution of individual parameters to the forecast skill was studied with an array of single parameter sensitivity tests using the parameter values of E1. These sensitivity tests were carried out in the same way as the verification of the model versions setting one parameter at a time to the optimised value and setting other parameters to default. It turned out that four parameters (CFM, DETRPEN, RPRCON, and RAMID) produce majority of the contribution. Most of the contribution to the wind and geopotential can be attributed to CFM. Most of the contribution to improvement of specific humidity, especially in the upper troposphere, comes from DETRPEN, RPRCON and RAMID. At the same time these three parameters act to balance the degradation of geopotential caused by CFM. Improvement of the upper tropospheric temperature can be mainly attributed to DETRPEN and RPRCON. Also, ZSIGQCW has a weak positive effect to most of the verified variables, especially at short and long forecast ranges. However, this kind of analysis obscures any potential compound effects caused by changing values of multiple parameters simultaneously. This is a potential reason for why DETRPEN appears to be an important parameter in the sensitivity tests, but insensitive during actual optimisation in E_{def} and E1.

In E1, the most pronounced improvements are related to specific humidity at 250 hPa and wind at 1000 hPa (not shown). In the case of specific humidity at 250 hPa, default OpenIFS tends to have a moist bias respect to operational analysis. The bias is strongest near the equator. However, there are areas of dry bias as well. E1 decreases the specific humidity globally, which decreases the moist bias by one fifth. However, in the areas of dry bias, the bias increases. The other aspect of OpenIFS improving significantly is the wind at 1000 hPa. Default OpenIFS has mostly too strong winds both in zonal and meridional directions except for the trade wind zones where the wind is too weak and too zonal. In E1 the wind speeds decrease in the most areas of the

globe, which is good in the mid and high latitudes but not in tropics. The fact that existence of such biases that cannot be alleviated with tuning, points to structural shortcomings in OpenIFS.

The optimised models E1 – E3 and E_{CFM} are verified also using higher resolution of T_L639. The parameter values obtained from the four main experiments (E1, E2, E3 and E_{CFM}) are verified using a set of 53 independent 10 days long forecasts initialised every seven days between Dec 2017 and Nov 2018. The default model and tuned models are compared to operational analysis using RMSE (Eq. (33)) and the results are again collected in scorecards. Fig. 9 shows the RMSE scorecards for the four main experiments using T_L639 resolution. In general, the scorecards show that the tuned parameters have a slight positive impact on several parameters in the short range but slight negative impact in medium to long range. On average the scorecards are neutral.

A couple of atmospheric fields are studied further to see the similarities and differences between T_L399 and T_L639 resolutions. The improvement of specific humidity at 250 hPa is very similar in both resolutions. The reason is that the bias structure is very similar in both default models, and the tuned parameters have very similar effect (not shown). In the contrary to T_L399, the 1000 hPa wind components do not improve much in T_L639 model (Fig. 9). The reason is that the T_L639 default model has clearly smaller and more localised biases than T_L399 default model (not shown). However, tuning decreases the wind speed globally in the same way as in the T_L399 case meaning that there are large areas where the tuned parameters induce new negative biases. The slight improvement of 1000 hPa U-wind seen in the scorecards appears to originate from a few areas in the tropical and sub-tropical oceans and the northern hemispheric storm tracks. The slight improvement of V-wind originates from a few localised areas in the extratropical oceans.

Based on the experiments shown so far, it seems that most of the parameter convergence occurs in the early part the optimization. Here, this information is used to run short tuning experiments ($O(50)$ steps) to examine possible correlations between the parameters in an empirical manner. The short experiments have random initial parameter values sampled from uniform distribution of [0.95, 1.05]. The initial variances are set to 0.1 (as in E1). The ensembles are initialised on 1 Dec 2016, 8 Dec 2016, ..., 30 Nov 2017 leading to 53 algorithm steps. These results are then compared against those given by EPPES. Fig. 10 (a) shows Pearson correlations computed from the four main experiments and the 10 additional short tuning experiments. In general, the empirical

Figure 9: Verification of the four main tuning experiments (E1, E2, E3 and E_{CFM}) with global root mean squared error using resolution of T_L639 . Blue color denotes improvement and red deterioration relative to the default model, and black dots mark statistical significance at 95% level. The atmospheric variables and pressure levels are the same as in Fig. 8. Adapted from Fig. 8 of **Paper III**.

correlations between the parameters appear to be relatively weak, but for a number of parameter pairs the correlation is statistically significant at 95% level. Many of the correlations are difficult to explain, but there are some physically intuitive examples as well. Two examples are explained here with the help of summary of physical processes in Section 2.2.2. ENTRORG and DETRPEN have statistically significant negative correlation. Both parameters are related to how efficiently the convective updraughts and

environmental air are mixing together. An increase of either parameter leads to more efficient mixing, which inhibits deep convection, and also leads to the convection being shallower. Thus, they can compensate each other naturally, and the correlation should be negative. ENTRORG and ENTSHALP are expected to be negatively correlated, since the entrainment of shallow convection is proportional to ENTSHALP multiplied with ENTRORG (see Eq. 14). Exactly that is seen in Fig. 10 (a) even though the correlation is not quite statistically significant.

The empirically obtained correlations are compared to correlations computed from the EPPES-given final covariance matrices of two tuning experiments E1 and E_{norank} , where E_{norank} differs from E1 only in that ranking of the cost function is inactive. Comparing the empirically obtained correlations to those obtained from final covariance matrices of two tuning experiments (Fig. 10) shows two important points. Firstly, EPPES tends to give substantially stronger correlations for the parameters, and secondly, the correlations change substantially from one experiment to another. The additional experiment without ranking of the cost function also shows that the overestimation of the correlations is not caused by the aggressive settings of EPPES in the other experiments. Comparison of Fig. 10 (b) and (c) shows that the correlations appear to be unrealistically strong regardless of the use of cost function ranking. Similar figures were created also from the 10 short tuning experiments, and in those figures the correlations seem to vary almost randomly between the experiments (not shown). It is difficult to see any physical reason for the unrealistically strong and random nature of the parameter correlations but it rather points to the incapability of EPPES to model the parameter covariances correctly in case of a fully-realistic NWP model. The degeneracy of the covariance matrix is not caused by the settings used in tuning but is caused by something more fundamental in the design of EPPES. The only useful information in the covariance matrix is how fast the uncertainties of the parameters are shrinking.

5.4 The future: observation-based optimisation

There are at least three reasons why the current moist total energy norm-based tuning methodology is insufficient. Firstly, Fig. 4 suggests that deterministic parameter values and the properties of ensemble forecasts are related. The methodology of **Papers II** and **III** does not accommodate this relationship. Secondly, the aim of tuning

Figure 10: Pearson correlations between parameter pairs. Panel (a) shows correlations computed based on the final parameter mean values of experiments E1, E2, E3, E_{CFM} and 10 additional short tuning experiments. CFM parameter has the land/sea separation in E_{CFM} , so for this purpose a global average of the two components has been taken. Statistical significance at 95% level is shown with black dots. Panel (b) shows correlations computed from the EPPES-given final parameter covariance matrix of experiment E1. Panel (c) shows the same as (b) for an experiment E_{norank} that does not use ranking of the cost function. Adapted from Fig. 10 of **Paper III**.

the model closure parameters is to balance the model so that the model output corresponds the reference state as well as possible. This statement implies that the reference state represents the truth. **Paper III** used operational analysis as the reference, be-

cause moist total energy norm ΔE_m requires the model and reference field to be of the same shape. However, operational analysis is still product of a model and may include model-induced biases (see e.g. Virman et al., 2021). Thirdly, ΔE_m is somewhat artificial construct, which gives different results depending on the weighting of the terms. Because of these three reasons, using a direct observation-based cost function is an attractive option for future tuning studies. **Paper IV** presents one promising option, the filter likelihood score (FLS). **Paper IV** shows how the quality of ensemble forecasts can be measured using FLS.

Fig. 11 presents a comparison of filter likelihood (panel (d)) to traditional verification with ensemble spread-skill without and with observation error accounted (panels (a) and (c)) and Dawid-Sebastiani score (panel (b)). The analysis is done for 500 hPa temperature in radio soundings and three different ensemble systems: EDA+SV, EDA and SV. The mean values of 45 ensemble forecasts are presented. Fig. 11 shows that filter likelihood is consistent with the traditional verification methods: the most comprehensive ensemble system (EDA+SV) is closest to the 1:1 ratio in spread-skill and the score of DSS and FLS is the lowest. FLS can be used to differentiate between different ensemble systems.

Fig. 12 presents a combined FLS for the Northern Hemisphere (NH) in panel (a), the tropical region (TR, 20N-20S) in panel (b) and the Southern Hemisphere (SH) in panel (c). FLS of Fig. 12 contains specific humidity at 500 and 850 hPa, and temperature and wind components at 200, 500 and 850 hPa pressure levels. Again, FLS can consistently differentiate between the three ensemble systems in the three different areas: EDA+SV has the lowest score.

Fig. 13 presents a combined FLS consisting of two different observation types: in-situ soundings and remote sensing satellite observations. Panel (a) shows FLS related to radiosonde measurements of temperature at 200, 500 and 850 hPa and specific humidity at 500 and 850 hPa for the three areas. Panel (b) shows FLS related to AMSU-A ch. 5 observations and panel (c) shows FLS computed from both radiosonde measurements used in panel (a) and AMSU-A ch. 5 measurements in panel (b). The ensemble system here is EDA+SV with SPPT. FLS behaves as expected: the score increases with increasing forecast lead time. An exception is the tropics where FLS for satellite data decreases initially. Differences in spatial distribution of observations can be seen from the values of FLS as FLS is averaged over all observations. There are more low FLS value producing soundings available in NH than the other areas so the FLS values

Figure 11: Different verification metrics for T500 in NH. Comparison between different verification metrics for temperature at 500 hPa in the Northern Hemisphere. The solid lines show the mean value of the metric and the shaded area two standard deviations. The green lines show forecasts with EDA and SV initial conditions, orange with EDA, and purple with SV. Adapted from Fig. 1 of **Paper IV**.

of NH shift down more in the combined score in NH than in the other areas. However, this is not a problem if different ensemble systems are compared using the same set of observations. To conclude, using combined FLS consisting of different observation types is possible.

Paper IV also tests FLS with different ensemble sizes. The results show that FLS is not a fair score. Instead, a larger ensemble size leads to lower (better) score (not shown).

Figure 12: Combined FLS consisting of specific humidity at 500 and 850 hPa levels, and temperature and wind components at 200, 500 and 850 hPa levels. Panel (a) shows the results for the northern hemisphere, panel (b) for the tropical region and panel (c) for the southern hemisphere. The green line shows EDA+SV, the orange EDA, and the purple SV. The solid line shows the mean value and the shaded area is two standard deviations. Adapted and modified from Fig. 2 panels (j), (k) and (l) of **Paper IV**.

6 Discussion and conclusions

This thesis has presented the fundamental building blocks of efficient algorithmic model optimisation. The tuning methodology of this thesis does not involve data assimilation, thus, rendering the optimisation set-up more flexible, simpler and less system dependent. The four papers included in this thesis exhibit a full story-line of algorithmic

Figure 13: FLS for both satellite and sounding observations. (a) Only sounding data, (b) Only satellite data, and (c) Combination of sounding and satellite data. Sum of different observation types: AMSU-A ch.5 brightness temperature and temperature at 200 hPa, 500 hPa, 850 hPa, and specific humidity at 500 hPa and 850 hPa for the ensemble system: EDA+SV+SPPT. The solid line shows the mean value over 53 ensemble forecasts and the shaded area two standard deviation error for three different areas: green for the Northern hemisphere, orange for the Tropics, and purple for the Southern Hemisphere. Adapted and modified from Fig. 3 of **Paper IV**.

optimisation: **Paper I** presents the development and testing of tools and data required for algorithmic optimisation, **Paper II** discusses how to maximise the efficiency of algorithmic optimisation, **Paper III** puts the tools, data and knowledge into practice in fully-realistic optimisation experiments and **Paper IV** discusses about a tools that can be used in algorithmic optimisation of model parameters in the future. Optimisation of an atmospheric model is an extremely complex and demanding task, so this thesis

advocates utilising algorithmic methods to at least provide a good starting point for further model development.

In order to enable easy and effortless design and administration of tuning experiments, a dataset of OpenIFS initial states and an ensemble workflow manager had to be crafted. **Paper I** presents the workflow manager OpenEPS and initial state dataset for three OpenIFS resolutions: T_L159 (~ 120 km), T_L399 (~ 50 km) and T_L639 (~ 32 km). The dataset covers one year (1 Dec 2016 to 30 Nov 2017) twice a day at 00 UTC and 12 UTC.

Using the initial state dataset and OpenEPS were demonstrated with ensemble forecast experiments covering all three horizontal resolutions and all three different initial state perturbation types. The experiments were verified using common ensemble verification metrics: spread-skill relationship and fair continuous ranked probability score (fCRPS). The experiments demonstrated that the initial states and the workflow management tool constitute a versatile platform for different kinds of academic ensemble forecasting set-ups to be used outside of the operational weather prediction centres; a feature further demonstrated in **Papers II, III and IV**.

The initial states and tools of **Paper I**, and two optimisation algorithms were used in a search for optimal set-up for algorithmic optimisation in **Paper II**. Designing algorithmic optimisation experiments has several aspects to consider: 1) the choice of cost function, (2) forecast range, (3) ensemble size and (4) the complexity of the model setup (initial state perturbations and stochastic physics turned on or off). The goal was to find an optimal setup of forecast range and ensemble size with the highest likelihood for fast and reliable convergence, hence minimising the amount of computations.

In order to highlight the importance of the choice of suitable cost function, two radically different cost functions were chosen: the root mean squared error of geopotential at 850 hPa and the moist total energy norm. The former was, as expected, a sub-optimal choice, whereas the latter was a clearly more suitable choice. However, the moist total energy norm was not a perfect choice either due to the properties of the tunable parameters. Different parameters work in different ways so selecting a cost function that is sensitive for all is a difficult task. **Paper II** gives an example with parameters controlling shallow entrainment θ_1 and deep organised entrainment θ_2 . θ_1 is mostly active only in the lowest 200 hPa in the model and mainly affects specific humidity in that layer whereas θ_2 is active in the entire troposphere and has direct impact on

wind, temperature and specific humidity throughout the model troposphere. Therefore, contribution of θ_2 to the cost function dominates, which may in some cases decrease the overall sensitivity of the moist total energy norm when estimating multiple parameters simultaneously.

Paper II found out that short forecast range (24 h) leads to the fastest parameter convergence. However, **Paper III** extends that slightly to 36 hours because the more diverse set of parameters included parameters showing better response with longer forecast ranges. Putting some effort on finding the optimal forecast range for the optimisation task at hand is beneficial also because the range impacts the robustness of the parameter convergence as shown in **Paper II**. **Paper II** also demonstrates that 20 members is the optimal ensemble size. Smaller ensemble can lead to too small sample size, and hence, possibly not having a representative sample and more unstable parameter convergence. In the contrary, larger ensembles were shown to not enhance the convergence enough to accommodate the increased computational cost. Interestingly, this result is in line with the conclusions of Leutbecher (2018) that in ensemble-forecasting-related research it is better to have a large number of relatively small ensembles than a small number of large ensembles. The most suitable level of complexity was determined to be such that initial state perturbations are activated but stochastic physics is deactivated. Initial state perturbations were shown to not hinder the parameter convergence while they bring additional diversity to the sampled weather states. Activation of stochastic physics, instead, was shown to slow the convergence down.

Paper III demonstrated using the tuning recipe of **Paper II** by studying whether it is possible to simultaneously estimate a large ($O(20)$) number of model parameters and achieve significant prediction skill improvement. **Paper III** presents fully-realistic optimisation experiments involving the deterministic values of the most important parameters of OpenIFS weather prediction model. Generally the optimisation works well even with 20 parameters that constitute a tough multidimensional problem. Moreover, most of the parameter convergence takes place early in the tuning experiments. The parameter mean values mostly converge during the first 50 algorithm steps. Instead, the parameter uncertainties continue decreasing for hundreds of steps. This means that algorithmic optimisation has some degree of flexibility as the number of algorithm steps can be chosen based on the user needs. However, the long-lasting decrease of uncertainty can also be seen as an over-fitting problem: the variability in the train-

ing material is limited, and the uncertainty reduction would probably not occur if the material with richer inter-annual variability was included. Nevertheless, based on evolution of parameter mean values, their uncertainties and the cost function value **Paper III** concludes that $O(100)$ steps is a good compromise between getting robust results and not using too much computational resources. This is more than what Dunbar et al. (2021) argue: They state that $O(100)$ model simulations is sufficient for model optimisation and uncertainty quantification with their methodology. The main experiments of **Paper III** used 122 steps with ensemble size of 20 totaling to 2440 model simulations.

It seems that every tuning experiment ends up in different optimal parameter values, and that the parameter values can differ up to 30% from the default parameter values. This was surprising as OpenIFS was expected to be a well-tuned model. There are several possible reasons why the changes can be so large. Firstly, the topography of the cost function can be complex and contain numerous local minima or it can be just relatively flat. Therefore, the inconsistency could be a manifestation of convergence to different local cost function minima. **Paper II** discussed about some conditions likely leading to getting stuck in a local minimum, most notably about having too large distance to optimum and too small initial uncertainty. Secondly, the inconsistency could also be caused by compensation of physical processes. For example the sensitivity testing in **Paper III** showed how it is to some extent possible to fix errors caused by modifications of one physical process by modifying another process. Thirdly, the hint that deterministic parameter values and the properties of ensemble forecasts are related suggests that the cost function formulation is missing something important. Fourthly, the experimentation revealed that EPPES does not treat the parameter covariances appropriately. The correlation figures and discussion in **Paper III** showed that covariances tend to degenerate in a random fashion. The degeneration of covariances may coerce the parameters to converge to a local optimum, and fifthly, the limited training material used in tuning (one year) may not represent a sufficiently rich selection of different weather types.

However, verification revealed that all optimised model versions outperform the model with default parameter values. Closer study of one of the optimised models showed that the most notable improvements in the model performance were related to 250 hPa specific humidity and 1000 hPa wind. Detailed inspection of these fields showed that optimisation can decrease certain systematic biases but can also reveal potential

structural shortcomings in the model such as the displacement errors in the 250 hPa specific humidity and too weak and too zonal trade winds at 1000 hPa. The optimisation of OpenIFS was carried out using horizontal resolution resolution of T_L399 but the optimised parameter values were tested with other resolutions as well focusing on T_L639. The tuned parameter values did not improve the T_L639 model largely due to resolution-dependent bias structures.

A peculiar finding encountered in **Paper II** and in additional experiments run during preparation of **Paper III** is that the choice of using initial state perturbations can affect the optimal parameter values. Model closure parameters can affect the ensemble spread. Using initial state perturbations in tuning apparently leads to such parameter values that suppress the growth of the perturbations. The initial results are interesting but the detailed discussion is left for the future. **Papers II** and **III**, however, show that perturbed initial states do not prevent the deterministic parameters converging towards optimum. Instead, the perturbations are thought to increase the sample diversity.

Another surprising finding was the variation of the parameter sensitivity between the tuning experiments. A good example is DETRPEN that shows almost no sensitivity in experiments E_{def} and E1 but is at least moderately sensitive in the other experiments. Both varying sensitivity and varying outcome may be manifestations of compensating processes. A way to control these two features could be useful since it would enable more precise tailoring of the cost function. However, this can lead to increased subjectivity of the tuning, which is against the spirit of algorithmic optimisation that is increasing the transparency of the tuning process (Hourdin et al., 2017).

A couple of other unfortunate results were discovered in **Paper III**. Firstly, the forecast range used in tuning (36 h) is clearly visible in Figs. 9 and 10 indicating that the parameter values are probably flow and lead-time dependent. This, in turn, suggests that OpenIFS might contain evolving systematic errors as well. The lead-time dependency hints that the cost function might need to be extended to evaluate forecast skill on multiple forecast ranges. Ollinaho et al. (2013) already tried combining different forecast ranges with limited results. However, the cost function they used was quite primitive in nature (mean squared error of 500 hPa geopotential). These evolving errors might be structural and, therefore, not possible to be fixed with tuning. Secondly, some model biases appear to be strongly resolution-dependent. The tuned parameter values may work only for the resolution that was used in tuning. A good example is the low-level wind speed. T_L399 default model tends to have too strong low-level wind in

majority of the globe, whereas T_{L639} has only local biases. Therefore, the parameter values intended for slowing the wind down in T_{L399} model slow the wind down also in wrong places in T_{L639} model. This finding decreases the prospect for applying the method of tuning a high-resolution model using lowered resolution.

Other limitations include, firstly, the low resolution used in tuning. 50 km resolution implies that several small-scale features are poorly represented both in the model and the analysis. Secondly, **Papers II** and **III** concentrate only on deterministic forecasts even though the deterministic parameters and the ability of maintaining spread in ensemble forecasts are clearly related to each other.

Papers II and **III** advocate algorithmic optimisation *per se* and as a tool to obtain parameter vector proposals for more close inspection by experts. **Paper III** tested if it is possible to enhance the results of algorithmic optimisation manually with a modest amount of effort. The results of experiments E1 – E3 and E_{CFM} were broken down together with the array of sensitivity experiments. The features leading to notable gain of skill were selected and combined leading to improvement of the average of the RMSE scorecard of E1 from -0.65% to -0.99% (not shown). EPPES outcomes can, hence, be used also as shortcuts in manual optimisation. This is in line with the conclusions of (Houtekamer et al., 2021): an expert can further optimise a model by interpreting the results of algorithmic optimisation.

Papers II and **III** indicated that the ensemble spread-skill is a fundamental feature to be taken into account even in optimisation of deterministic parameters. Moreover, the moist total energy norm-based tuning methodology may be difficult to improve further for future tuning experiments. Constraining the ensemble spread is beyond the capabilities of the method. An attractive option for cost function is an observation-based verification metric called filter likelihood score (FLS) that is presented in **Paper IV**. FLS was shown to be capable of differentiating between ensemble forecasts having different configurations. Therefore, it seems to be able to penalise such seemingly optimal parameter values correctly that have undesired effect on ensemble forecasts.

The ensemble forecast verification experiments showed that FLS is consistent with traditional verification metrics and can differentiate between set-ups of an ensemble forecasting system. The results also showed that FLS can be applied both as a univariate and combined score, and it can accommodate multiple observation types simultaneously. This was demonstrated by combining in-situ radio soundings with remote

sensing observations of AMSU-A channel 5. Limitations of FLS include that it does not give details about the bias and the spread. It can only tell if the bias is positive or negative, or if the ensembles are under- or overdispersive. Moreover, FLS is not a fair score meaning that the ensemble size affects the score. However, these limitations will not be a problem in tuning applications since tuning algorithms need only to know if bias and spread are correct or not, and future tuning will be performed with fixed ensemble size in the same way as in **Papers II** and **III**.

FLS is an approximation in the sense that observation error covariances are set to zero meaning that the observations are assumed to be fully independent. Firstly, this assumption makes the computation easier and faster facilitating future algorithmic tuning implementations, and secondly, the issue of having an ensemble of much smaller size than the number of observations is avoided. Goodness of the observation error estimates also affects FLS. Operational observation operators were not used, so the results may be affected by the interpolation methods used in the computation of model counterparts in observation space. For example Ferro (2017) uses error-convolved logarithmic score, which is a special case of FLS, to illustrate how quality of the observations affects the assessment of a forecast system.

At the end, the author hopes that this thesis provides ideas and inspiration for the reader for further work on algorithmic optimisation based on ensemble forecasting.

7 Review of papers and the author's contribution

Paper I presents an OpenIFS initial state dataset and OpenEPS software for running ensemble forecasts in academic environments. Using the initial states and the ensemble forecasting software is demonstrated with various examples. The author participated in development and testing of OpenEPS and served as a quality controller during the production of the initial states. The author also contributed to writing the manuscript.

Paper II investigates ways to make algorithmic optimisation of deterministic model parameters more efficient. The findings are compressed into a cook-book style recipe for computationally efficient algorithmic optimisation experiments. The author carried out all numerical experimentation and produced all figures. The author also wrote majority of the manuscript.

Paper III presents fully-realistic examples of OpenIFS parameter optimisation using the recipe of **Paper II**. 19 (20) parameters are optimised simultaneously for a number of times, and performance of the optimised model versions are compared to the original model version. The author carried out all numerical experiments, produced all figures and wrote most of the manuscript.

Paper IV presents fully-realistic examples of using filter likelihood score in verification of OpenIFS ensemble forecasts. Different versions of filter likelihood score are presented and are compared to more traditional ensemble forecast verification methods. The author produced the model counterparts for AMSU-A channel 5 observations and participated in writing the manuscript.

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